

FLEXURAL DEFORMATION OF THE CNT ARRAY AS A MEASURE OF VAN DER WAALS INTERACTION FORCES

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SUMMARY: The flexural stiffness of the hexagonal carbon nanotube (CNT) array is shown to directly correlate with the magnitude of the shearing traction between the individual CNT and thereby provide a convenient measurement of van der Waals forces in the CNT hexagonal array. Relationships for flexural stiffness and shearing traction are developed systematically illustrated for the 7, 61 and 127-element arrays. Shearing traction is calculated for a lateral load sufficient to produce lateral deflection of the array equal to one percent of the span length. Both fixed-fixed and simple-simple beam end conditions are examined. Model predictions are combined with the experimental results of Salvetat et al [3] to determine the magnitude of the maximum shearing traction due to van der Waals forces in each of the arrays. Shearing tractions are shown to vary from 20.0 to 1.6 MPa over the range in number of array elements from 7 - 127 and array heights from 4.7 to 19.7 nm. These new results suggest that the van der Waals interactions will likely provide array coherence and cohesiveness sufficient for the CNT arrays of a smaller number of elements to serve as effective reinforcements in high performance materials.

KEYWORDS: Carbon nanotubes, hexagonal arrays, flexural, van der Waals forces, shearing traction

INTRODUCTION

The present study is an experimental validation of analyses described in the authors' earlier publications [1] and was motivated by the investigation of Salvetat et al described in reference [4] wherein the ratio of flexural deformation to applied load of the CNT array (rope) was used to determine a reduced Young's modulus and effective shearing modulus of the CNT array. Results were presented that showed Young's modulus of the CNT array to decrease with increase in array size (diameter) and this decrease was attributed to shearing deformation. The authors of the present study describe a mechanism that accounts for the dependence of the flexural compliance of the CNT array on the shearing tractions between the individual CNT due to van der Waals forces. In the present study the Young's modulus of the CNT of a given chirality (n,m) is taken as that predicted in reference [2]. Next a model is developed wherein the influence of the shearing traction upon the flexural compliance of the hexagonal array is determined.

It will now be shown that the flexural stiffness of the carbon nanotube (CNT) array can be taken as a direct measure of the magnitude of the Van der Waals interaction forces between the individual CNT. Consider the hypothetical case where the van der Waals interaction forces are absent. In such a condition, the flexural stiffness of the array is the simple sum of the flexural stiffnesses of the individual CNT.

However, as the shearing traction between the CNT increases, the flexural stiffness, (P/δ) of the array also increased. In the following an analysis is presented for the flexural compliance of a hexagonal array consisting of “N” CNT with the magnitude of the shearing tractions acting between the CNT in the array adjusted by the variable, k , the shear transfer efficiency.

EXPRESSIONS FOR THE N-ELEMENT HEXAGONAL ARRAY OF CNT

The flexural compliance (deflection-force response) for the N -element hexagonal array of CNT subjected to a central lateral load of P_T (Figure 1) can be expressed as follows [1]:

$$\frac{\delta}{P_T} = \frac{L^3}{100jE_n} \left[(A_N + B_N k) D_{na}^4 \right]^{-1}$$

$$j = 1.92 \quad \text{fixed - fixed}$$

$$j = 0.48 \quad \text{simple - simple}$$
(1)

The number of elements, N in an array of order, M (an integer) is given by:

$$N = \left[\sum_{n=1}^M 6n \right] + 1$$
(2)

Figure 1 Fixed-fixed, seven-element carbon nanotube array geometry.

The relationship given in equation (1) is developed by replacing the N -element hexagonal array of CNT by a laminate of equivalent flexural compliance and consisting of “ N_L ” layers of variable width, b_m . The relationship between the number of elements, N in the hexagonal array and the number of layers, N_L appropriate to its representation is:

$$N_L = 2M + 1 \quad (3)$$

Equation (2-3) show that hexagonal arrays may consist of $N = 7, 19, 37, 61, 91, 127, 169, 217, 331$...individual SWCN and the number of layers necessary to represent the hexagonal array as layered beam is 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13 ...

The magnitudes shearing tractions between the individual layers of the laminate can be continuously varied between the fully bonded condition ($k = 1$) and the unbonded condition ($k = 0$). In addition, the maximum interlaminar shearing traction can be shown to occur between the $m-1$ and m layers of the laminate:

$$\tau = \frac{kP_0 C_N}{2I_T b_{m-1}} \quad (4)$$

Where the force, P_0 corresponding to a deflection equal to one percent of the span length, L is:

$$P_0 = \frac{jE_n}{L^2} [A_N + kB_N] D_{na}^4$$

$$j = 1.92 \quad \text{fixed - fixed} \quad (5)$$

$$j = 0.48 \quad \text{simple - simple}$$

And where the coefficients given in Equation (1) are:

$$A_N = \sum_{i=1}^{ii-1} 2I_i + I_{ii} \quad B_N = 2 \sum_{i=1}^{ii-1} A_i Y_i^2 \quad C_N = \sum_{i=1}^{ii-1} A_i Y_i$$

$$ii = \frac{N_L + 1}{2}, \quad N_L = \text{number of layers (must be odd)} \quad (6)$$

The coefficients A_N , B_N and C_N for the 7, 19, 37, 61 and 127 element arrays are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Coefficients for general expression equation (6).

N	A_N	B_N
7	0.3436	2.356
19	0.9327	18.85
37	1.816	73.04
61	2.994	200.3
127	6.234	874.2

The results presented in Table 1 can be evaluated for the (18,0) SWCN as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Coefficients for (18,0) SWCN array equation (1).

N	$A_N(D_{na})^4$	$B_N(D_{na})^4$
7	3.056	20.96
19	8.297	167.7
37	16.16	649.7
61	26.64	1782
127	55.46	7775

COMPARISON TO EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Salvetat et al [4] utilized atomic force microscopy to measure the flexural compliance of SWCN arrays (ropes). In the interpretation of their measurements, the authors showed a reduction in Young's modulus from 1310 GPa, for an array (rope) diameter of 3 nm, to 67 GPa for a diameter of 20 nm. Salvetat et al also stated that the mean diameter of the SWCN in the arrays tested was 1.4 nm. The (18,0) SWCN has been shown earlier to correspond to a diameter of 1.409 nm with an effective diameter in the array of D_{ne} of 1.727 nm (1.409 + 0.318 nm) and a corresponding value of Young's modulus equal to 618.3 GPa [2].

Taking the effective SWCN diameter, D_{ne} to be 1.727 nm leads to dimensions of the various arrays shown in Table 3.

Table 3 (18,0) SWCN array geometry.

Elements	Array Height (nm)	Array Width (nm)
7	4.7	5.2
19	7.7	8.6
37	10.7	12.1
61	13.7	15.5
91	16.7	19.0
127	19.7	22.4

Salvetat et al examined the flexural response of arrays that correspond closely to the 7, 61 and 127 SWCN hexagonal arrays shown in Table 2 and Figure 2 with model hexagonal array heights of 4.7, 13.7 and 19.7 nm as compared to measured diameters of 4.5, 13.5 and 20.0 nm, respectively.

Figure 2 Seven, sixty-one and one hundred twenty-seven element hexagonal carbon nanotube array.

The results experimental presented in reference [4] for the deflection/load response of the 7, 61 and 127-element SWCN arrays were utilized to determine the magnitude of the load transfer efficiencies and shearing tractions for each array. It should be noted that each spanned nano-sized holes (span length) in a polished alumina ultrafiltration membrane. The authors of reference [4] assumed that the end conditions for the arrays were fixed at each end (fixed-fixed) due to the attraction of the continuous array to the filter surface. The consequences of this assumption will be discussed later.

The results for the 7-element array of span lengths of 285 and 180 nm correspond to $k = 0.85$ and 0.64 , respectively (Table 4). If the two values are averaged, the result is $k = 0.74$. The sensitivity of the predictions to the parameter, k is shown in Figure 3.

The magnitudes of the maximum shearing traction in the 7-element arrays were determined to be 13.6 and 20.0 MPa, for an average of 16.8 MPa. Here the load for calculation of the maximum shearing traction was chosen to correspond to an array deflection equal to 1 percent of the span length – well within the regime of linear response.

The magnitude of the shearing tractions for the 7-element array show that van der Waals forces acting between the individual SWCN in the array are significant and sufficient to decrease the fixed-fixed bending compliance (δ/P) of the 7-element array with 285 nm span from 63.7 to 9.3 – a 650 percent reduction.

Table 4 Array results.

Array Element Number	Span (10 ⁻⁹ m)	Force (10 ⁻¹⁰ N)	Width, <i>b</i> (10 ⁻⁹ m)	<i>Q</i> (10 ⁻²⁷ m)	<i>I</i> (10 ⁻³⁶ m)	<i>k</i>	Shearing Traction (x10 ⁶ N/m ²)
7	285	3.1	2.79	7.01	24.0	0.85	13.6
7	180	6.0	2.79	7.01	24.0	0.64	20.0
61	360	48.0	14.1	209.4	1808.2	0.28	5.5
127 FF	370	74.0	18.8	637.6	7831.4	0.10	1.6
127 SS	370	24.7	18.8	637.6	7831.4	0.31	5.0

FF: Fixed-Fixed, SS: Simple-Simple

Figure 3 Load transfer efficiency versus array deflection/load ratio for different (18,0) SWCN array sizes.

The 61-element array calculated thickness for a SWCN diameter of 1.727 nm is 13.69 nm and corresponds closely to the 13.5 diameter array described in reference (4) for a span length of 360 nm. Two results for array compliance (δ/P_T) are reported, 1.0 and 0.5 m/N. If the two values are averaged, the result is 0.75 m/N which corresponds to a load transfer efficiency of $k = 0.279$. It is important to note that the form of equation (1) yields only modest sensitivity of δ/P_T to k for values of $k > 0.25$. The load, P_0 corresponding to a deflection of 3.6 nm for an array span of 360 nm is 48.0×10^{-10} N and the shearing traction between layers 4 and 5 at that load in the 61-element array is 25.6×10^6 N/m².

The 127-element array model represents the 20.0 nm diameter array with span of 370 nm in reference [4] where experimental result reported was 0.5 m/N. This value corresponds to $k = 0.103$ for the fixed-fixed end conditions and 0.309 for simple-simple conditions as shown in Table 4. It is noteworthy that the authors of reference [4] chose the fixed-fixed end conditions in their analysis of all array sizes tested. Yet it is likely that the magnitude of the van der Waals attraction between the filter substrate and the CNT array could vary significantly with array size and would decrease in importance as array size is increased. Therefore, the results for the two end conditions presented in Table 4 can be thought of as the upper and lower bounds on actual large array compliances. The shearing traction corresponding to a deflection of 3.7 nm and lateral force, $P_0 = 74 \times 10^{-10}$ N was 18.0×10^6 N/m² for both the fixed-fixed and simple-simple cases.

While the shearing traction ratio results for the three arrays of 7, 61 and 127 of 1.4 nm diameter SWCN and of 0.850, 0.279 and 0.103, respectively differ, all experimental results fall within the range $0 < k < 1.0$ for each of the array predictions.

When the shearing traction values from Table 4 and the shearing moduli values determined by Salvetat et al [3] are normalized, they can be compared as shown in Table 5. Here we see that the trend for reduction in modulus with increase in array size is shown to coincide with a corresponding reduction in shearing traction.

Table 5 Normalized Shearing Modulus and Traction.

N Element Array	Shear Modulus Ratio, [3]	Load Transfer Efficiency Ratio
7	-	1.00
7	1.00	0.75
61	0.28	0.33
127	0.11	0.12

In addition, it is possible to determine the shearing strain in each array corresponding to the ratio of the shearing traction to the shearing modulus as shown in Table 6. What is striking is that the shearing strain for the three array geometries is very nearly equal (average of 2779×10^{-6}) although the array sizes range from 4.7 to 19.7 nm in height.

Table 6 Array Shearing Strain.

N Element Array	Shear Modulus [3]	Shearing Traction	Shearing Strain
7	6.50	20.0	3077
61	1.85	5.5	2973
127	0.70	1.6	2286

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The motivation for the present study was the investigation described in reference [4] wherein the flexural deformation of the CNT array was used to determine its reduced Young's modulus and effective shearing modulus. When the authors of reference [4] chose to attribute the reduced flexural stiffness of the CNT array to shearing deformation, they did so in accordance with classical beam analysis, wherein homogeneous beam geometries with large shearing stresses compared to flexural stresses or materials of low shearing modulus, can produce appreciable shearing deformation that contributes to the overall beam deflection. When Young's modulus is determined by the slope of the beam load-deflection curve, the contribution of shearing deformation to overall beam deflection must be considered for a homogeneous beam. Salvetat [4] pointed out that if the CNT exhibit no interaction, their Young's modulus "...would be higher than 10 TPa for our data." Indeed, calculations reveal that the CNT moduli would have been 4.2 TPa, 12.2 TPa and 9.5 TPa in the 7, 61 and 127-element arrays, respectively, to provide the observed flexural compliances of the arrays. While the shearing tractions between the CNT do decrease the compliance of the array, in no case were the tractions found to be of a level consistent the deformation of a homogeneous beam (fully bonded). Therefore, the assumption that the CNT array can be represented as a uniform beam is not appropriate for CNT arrays. It has been shown that since the Young's modulus of the CNT is uniquely determined by its chiral vector (n,m) [2], it is the magnitude of shearing traction between the CNT due to van der Waals forces that controls the flexural compliance of the array. In the case of the 127-element array, the flexural stiffness was 1500 percent greater than the combined flexural stiffnesses of the 127 CNT. Had the shearing traction been sufficient to achieve full bonding of the CNT, the increase would have been 14,100 percent.

Models for the flexural compliance of the hexagonal CNT array have been developed. Flexural compliance of the hexagonal carbon nanotube (CNT) array has been shown to be inversely proportional to the magnitude of the shearing traction between the individual CNT and thereby provide a convenient measurement of van der Waals forces in the CNT hexagonal array. Relationships for flexural compliance and shearing traction were given for the general hexagonal array of CNT consisting of 7, 19, 37, 61, 127, 192, ...individual elements. The experimental results of Salvetat [4] for the 7-element array (4.5 nm diameter rope) with span lengths of 285 and 180 nm, revealed shearing tractions of 13.6 and 20.0 MPa, respectively, for a deflection equal to one percent of the span. The magnitude of the shearing traction was found to be 5.5 MPa for the 61-element array (13.5 nm diameter) and 1.6/5.0 MPa for the 127-element array (20 nm diameter).

The load transfer efficiency, k was found to vary from 0.85 for the 7-element array to 0.1 for the 127-element array, while the magnitude of the shearing traction also correspondingly decreased (20.0 - 1.5 MPa). However, when the compliance of the three arrays is examined as a function of the parameter, k , compliance showed little sensitivity in the region $k > 0.1$ and small measurement errors could easily be magnified. Considering the three arrays: 7, 61 and 127 elements, the ratio of the array compliance for $k = 0$ to the compliance corresponding to $k = 0.1$ was 1.69, 7.69 and 15.02, respectively. These results show that the compliance of the array is significantly reduced for $0 \leq k \leq 0.1$ for all array sizes, but this trend is especially pronounced as the array size is increased as shown in Figure 3. This result shows that a shearing traction magnitude considerably less than that required for full bonding is sufficient to reduce the array compliance in agreement with experimental observations.

Salvetat et al [4] stated that, "...the low shear modulus of SWCT ropes is bad news for potential applications such as reinforcement of materials..." Yet the magnitude of shearing traction determined for the 7-element array (average of 16.8 MPa) is comparable to the adhesive bond strength in high performance applications. In addition, the work of Saether et al [5] has revealed effective properties of the SWCN hexagonal array in the plane transverse to the array direction that exceed those of the carbon

fiber/epoxy composite. These new results suggest that the van der Waals interactions will likely provide array coherence and cohesiveness sufficient for the CNT array with smaller number of elements to serve as an effective reinforcement in high performance materials.

Both the normalized shearing traction and the array shearing modulus, as determined by Salvetat [4], were shown to decrease with increase in array size. As a result, the array shearing strain was shown to be very nearly constant (average 2779×10^{-6}) for the three arrays (7, 61 and 127 elements) when subjected to a deflection equal to 1% of the span length. This behavior was an unexpected result not previously observed. Yet the confirmation of these results and their full understanding await additional reproducible experimental results.

REFERENCES

- [1] Pipes, R.B. and Hubert, "The Influence of Shearing Traction on the Flexural Deformation of CNT Arrays," in review, *Composites Science and Technology*, (2003).
- [2] Pipes, R.B., Frankland, S., Hubert, P., and Saether, E., "Self Consistent Properties of the SWCN and its Hexagonal Arrays as Composite Reinforcements," in press, *Composites Science and Technology* (2002).
- [3] Pipes, R.B. and Hubert, P., "Self-Consistent Geometry, Density and Stiffness of Carbon Nanotubes," *Proceedings of the 17th Annual Conference of the American Society for Composites*, (2002).
- [4] Salvetat, J. -P., Briggs, G.A.D., Bonard, J. -M., Bacsá, R.R., Kulik, A.J., Stockli, T., Burnham, N.A. and Forro, Laszlo, "Elastic and Shear Moduli of Single-Walled Carbon Nanotube Ropes," *Physical Review Letters*, Vol. 82, No. 5, (1999), pp.944-947.
- [5] Saether, E., Frankland, S.J.V. and Pipes, R.B. "Nanostructured Composites: Effective Mechanical Property Determination of Nanotube Bundles," *Proceedings of the 43rd AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference*, Denver, (2002).

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